

SWEET Call 1-2021: SWICE

Deliverable report

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Summary

This document summarizes the work and findings of sub-task T3.2.2.1 of the SWEET-SWICE project [1], conducted from March 2024 to November 2024 at EMPA-ALCA. More specifically, it presents a life cycle assessment (LCA) of the Eglantine Neighborhood in the city of Morges in the canton of Vaud.

Using a versatile and iterative approach, the present work provides a diagnosis of the key environmental hotspots for an urban territory of neighborhood size.

The Eglantine Neighborhood combines the advantages of a contemporary building complex with high environmental and social standards. It also provides a unique feature that simplify the development of the LCA model since all infrastructures and buildings were developed at the same time. It is a particularly relevant case for evaluating what the future might hold for Swiss sustainable neighborhoods developed with current "best practices" (e.g. Minergie quality label).

The obtained results present a hotspot analysis to identify key sources of potential environmental impacts. More promising changes from an environmental perspective are also discussed, as are the limits to the applicability of the LCA approach to other urban territories.

1 Introduction

SWICE [1], a major Swiss national project lasting eight years and involving collaboration between various academic and non-academic partners, aims to identify and quantify energy-saving potentials and opportunities for enhancing quality of life through future urban and building scenarios. It places significant emphasis on human well-being as a crucial element of the urban energy transition and seeks to propose environmental and technological solutions in three key areas of change: the built environment, open spaces, and mobility, with people seen as the main drivers of change in the ongoing energy transition.

Many aspects need to be considered and modelled to carry out the SWICE project [1]. When it comes to quantify environmental burdens, the life cycle assessment (LCA) method is recognized as a performant option to analyze the different potential impacts associated with all stages of a life cycle for systems, products, or services. This is why the Work Package 3 of the SWICE project [1] attempts to provide a guiding framework for applying the LCA method to an urban territory (i.e. "system") with the main goal of developing general recommendations for the transition to more environmentally sustainable neighborhoods in Switzerland.

This document details the implementation of a LCA study and its first iteration. The LCA method has been applied to Eglantine, a sustainable neighborhoods in Morges - Western Switzerland, that serves as a Living Lab in the SWICE project. The study identifies the main environmental hotspots among the different components of a neighborhood, i.e. buildings, open spaces, mobility, energy, as well as the food and consumption of households.

The document begins with a description of the case study (i.e. Eglantine) in Section 2.1. A summarized introduction of the LCA method is then presented to provide more context (Section 2.2). Then, the goal and scope definition of the present study is thoroughly described respectively in section 2.3 and 2.4. In this section, the selection and the sources of data are discussed as well as the different models used. Section 2.5 delves into the obtained LCA results for the Eglantine neighborhood with the identification of various hotspots. Initial recommendations are also presented to reduce the environmental footprint of the Eglantine neighborhood. Finally, the limits of the study and recommendations for potential use of the same method to other neighborhoods are discussed in Section 2.6. The document ends with a conclusion to the study (Section 3).

2 Deliverable content

2.1 Case study description

The Eglantine neighborhood is located in the city of Morges, in the western part of Switzerland. This is a complex of buildings (14 postal addresses) whose construction in the unbuilt zone was initiated by a participatory process in 2014 and completed between the summer 20219 and 2022 (See Figure 1). The area concerned is bounded to the north by avenue Warnery, to the west by the commune boundary with Chigny, to the south by chemin de la Mottaz and to the east by chemin de Tolochenaz. The main features of the case study are summarized in Table 1. The Eglantine neighborhood and its stakeholders are the subject of a report issued for the SWICE project [2].

Figure 1: Sky view of Eglantine neighborhood [2].

List of features	Quantity	Unit
Surface of the site (buildings + open spaces)	40'800	m ²
Energy reference area	47'997	m ² _{SRE}
Household	473	-
Number of employments	22,3	FTE
Average customers per operating day	358	person

Table 1: main features of Eglantine, source: "Rapport Cockpit -Sites 2000W" (2023) [3].

2.2 Introductory overview of life cycle assessment principles

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a recognized method of analyzing the potential environmental impacts of systems and products. LCA enables the environmental assessment of the object of study (i.e. neighborhood) over the different phases of its life cycle, such as manufacturing and use phase starting from the extraction of raw materials until the final disposal stage - i.e. the cradle to grave perspective.

ISO 14040 [4] defines the evaluation process, which comprises four stages (see Figure 2): Defining the objectives and scope of the study (see respectively Section 2.3 and 2.4), the Life cycle inventory (LCI) (see Supplementary material 1), the Environmental impact assessment, and the interpretation of the results (see section 2.5). An iterative principle is applied in which all choices made in the different stages can evolve after an analysis of their effects on the relevance of LCA to answer the defined objectives.

Figure 2: the four stages of LCA [4].

2.3 Goal definition

Here are six main aspects of the goal definition [5]:

Indented application: This LCA study identifies the key environmental hotspots of the selected neighborhood (i.e. Eglantine) when looking at the full life cycle of all its components.

Reason for carrying the study: The main reason for the LCA study is to develop general recommendations for moving towards more sustainable neighborhoods in Switzerland. The choice of Eglantine as a case study is explained by the quote from [2]: "*reason we chose Eglantine as a case study is due to the opportunity offered by another R&D ongoing project (DevQuad, Radu 2024) developed by TRANSFORM and ENERGY institutes (HEIA-FR) and that aims at verifying the MODD project's desired results in terms of social mixing and of energy efficiency.*"

Target audience: the members of the SWEET-SWICE research consortium, SFOE representatives, and neighborhood stakeholders.

Comparisons intended to be disclosed to the public: Since the results of the LCA analysis are intended to enable the co-creation of scenarios that are both effective in terms of environmental gains and acceptable to the neighborhood's stakeholders, it goes without saying that the results will be communicated to them. No comparison with other neighborhoods is planned at this stage of the project.

Limitation of the study: Only five categories of environmental indicators are presented because the selected background database (see Section 2.4.1) is limiting the access to more detailed descriptions of impact categories. The data availability is another point of concerns (see section 2.4.1). The strategy to deal with this limitation is the assessment of optimistic and pessimistic alternatives for determining the involved uncertainties.

Commissioner of the study and other influential actors: The Swiss Federal Office of Energy is the commissioner of the study. The work is performed within the SWICE WP3 activities led by Prof. F. Radu (TRANSFORM institute, HEIA-FR) and Prof. C. Fivet (SXL-EPFL).

2.4 Scope definition

Concerning the scope of the study, the following key features are defined:

The **system to be analyzed** is the Eglantine neighborhood as defined in section 2.1. The temporal horizon is set at 60 years, which correspond to the reference study period defined in the Swiss standards SIA 2040 [6] and SIA 3032 [7].

The System boundary: Elements considered in our study and what is not taken in account is detailed in Figure 3. The classification of the various components into different layers is also represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: System boundary of the study.

The functional unit: The infrastructure, services and goods necessary for a year of residents' activities in the Eglantine neighborhood of Morges, Switzerland for the period between 2022 and 2082. This functional unit is also linked in the LCA results to the buildings' reference surface for residential and commercial activities.

The selection of **impact categories** is directly linked to the selection of the background database (i.e. KBOB [8] – See Section 2.4.1) and the selected impact assessment methods are detailed in Table 2:

Impact category	Impact assessment methods
Cumulative energy demand describing the consumption of fossil, nuclear and renewable energy sources.	Implementation according to Frischknecht et al. (2007) [9], in [kWh oil-eq].
Renewable part of the cumulative energy demand describing the consumption of renewable energy sources (hydro, solar, wind, geothermal, biomass).	Implementation according to Frischknecht et al. (2007) [9], in [kWh oil-eq].
Non-renewable part of the cumulative energy demand describing the consumption of non-renewable energy sources (fossil and nuclear).	Implementation according to Frischknecht et al. (2007) [9], in [kWh oil-eq].

Eco-points 2021, evaluating the inventory results on a distance to target principle. The calculation of the eco-factors is based on one hand on the actual emissions (actual flow) and on the other hand on Swiss environmental policy and legislation (critical flow) [10].	Swiss Ecological Scarcity Method 2021 [11] in [UBP]
Greenhouse gas emissions	The greenhouse effect is quantified on the basis of the warming potential referred to in the IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report (2013) [12] in [kg CO ₂ -eq/kg]. Biogenic CO ₂ is considered to be carbon neutral. Its global warming potential is thus set at 0 kg CO ₂ -eq/kg.

Table 2: impact categories and impact assessment methods used in the study.

2.4.1 Data

Foreground data used to model the neighborhood comes mainly from the “Rapport Cockpit -Sites 2000W” [3], the re-certification document of the 2000 watts label application in 2023, from the Minergie Certification Dossier [13], as well as the technical report on the energy concept [14]. When contradictory information was found in these files, the most recent information was taken into consideration. To compensate the problems linked to a lack of data representativeness or availability (i.e. when the information required for the LCA models was not presented in the reference documents), the necessary data points were estimated from different visual documents. In that spirit, free-access photos, illustrations and drawings available on the websites of the architects, planners and owners involved in the construction project [15-20] were used as well as pictures taken during a photography campaign on site (see supplementary material 2). Geographic Information System (GIS) data from the Confederation's website [15] was also used for measuring elements of the open space <OS> layer, and certain quantitative information such as the number of apartments came from the Federal Register of Buildings and Dwellings RegBL (See Supplementary material 3).

Concerning **the background data**, the choice of the database is based on the following criteria: availability; compatibility with the context of the case study, large coverage in term of applicability. Two possible candidates were susceptible to be used, at least for the first LCA iteration, namely the KBOB [8] (available in Supplementary material 4) or the UVEK database [22], both published by the Swiss Confederation. The main features of both databases are presented in Table 3:

	KBOB [8]	UVEK DQR v2 [16]
Positive aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Open access. -Edited by the Swiss government. -Simple to use. -Updated regularly. -Specific to the building sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Edited by the Swiss government. -Possibility to perform Monte-Carlo analysis to consider uncertainty ranges of the input data and the results of LCA calculations. -Updated regularly. -Offers disaggregated information on processes of supply chains with details on emissions of pollutants and extraction of natural resources. -Possibility to use various impact assessment methods (e.g. ReCiPe)
Negative aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Limited to 5 impact category indicators (i.e. Swiss ecological scarcity, CED, CED_R; CED_{NR}; GHG emissions) -No possibility to perform Monte-Carlo analysis and thus no possibility to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Necessity to use an LCA software tool such a OpenLCA or SimaPRO. - more complex to handle than KBOB. - Cannot be used by all other members of the SWICE consortium. (No possibility to be reused, nor to be checked)

inform on the uncertainty linked to the models and LCA calculations.

-Absence of datasets describing the infrastructure related to water.

-No possibility to specifically inform on the potential biodiversity change from the neighborhood's infrastructure and its activities.

Provided macro-elements describing the building sectors are limiting the capacity to identify specific environmental hotspots on some materials.

Table 3: Comparison of the main features of the KBOB [8] and the UVEK background database [22].

Despite the quite long list of drawbacks in comparison with the UVEK database, the choice has been taken to use the KBOB database at least for the first iteration of Eglantine. The main reason is to insure the availability of the database through the whole scientific consortium at no cost. The KBOB database regroups the life cycle environmental data of standard elements and macro-elements in the construction sector, as well as those for means of transportation and energies.

The necessary **background data for the food and consumption layers** is based on the assessment of the greenhouse gas footprint for households by category of expenditure [17] published by the Swiss office of statistics for the year 2021. This assessment is obtained by a top-down input-output framework.

2.4.2 LCA Models

Our model of the Eglantine neighborhood considers buildings, energy uses, mobility, open spaces, as well as the food intake and the other consumption of residents. Each of these dimensions are so called layers. They correspond to the different branches presented in Figure 3: System boundary of the study. The developed model is hybrid in the sense that it combines LCA data based on a bottom-up LCA approach (layers , <OS>, <E>), and data coming from a top-down approach (layers <M>, <C> and <F>).

2.4.2.1 The layer "Buildings"

The neighborhood consists of twelve buildings that make up the Eglantine neighborhood (14 postal addresses and therefore 14 entries in the RegBL – See supplementary material 4). After consultation with the WP3 partners, it was decided that the underground parking lot would be considered in the building layer. The latter also serves as a possible shelter for the population in the event of a disaster and was modeled using the relevant technical recommendations from the government [18].

The structure used to model buildings in this study is the one depicted in the standard SN EN 15804 [19], See Figure 4.

Étapes selon SN EN 15804	Étape de production			Étape de construction	Étape d'utilisation							Étape de fin de vie				
	Approvisionnement en matières premières	Transport	Fabrication	Transport	Processus de construction-installation	Utilisation	Maintenance	Réparation	Remplacement	Réhabilitation	Utilisation opérationnelle de l'énergie	Utilisation opérationnelle de l'eau	Démolition/Déconstruction	Transport	Traitement des déchets	Élimination
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	C1	C2	C3	C4
Domaine «construction» selon SIA 2032	x	x	x	(x)	(x)				x				x	x	x	x

Figure 4: The different stages of the assessment for the building layer according to SN EN 15804 [19] and SIA 2032 [7].

Module A1-3 (production phase): The assessment is made by combining bills of materials for the buildings (available in the supplementary material 2) with the KBOB database [8]. The construction elements taken in account are presented in Figure 3, as well as those neglected. A comparison with scope definition for buildings in other countries is presented in Appendix 1 as a frame of reference on the comprehensiveness of our model. Elements that could not be accurately assessed on the basis of the information received were modeled using optimistic and pessimistic ranges. For more details, see Appendix 2. Infrastructure belonging to the building service (e.g. ventilation system) and to deliver energy (e.g. heating distribution system) are taken in account in the layer Energy. Information on the composition of the walls is provided in the Minergie file, and the measurements were mainly taken from this file, or measured on photographic surveys (supplementary material 2 and/or [15-20]). No information was provided for buildings <B1> and <B10>. The necessary information has thus been extrapolated either from the building stock built by the same architect (for <B1>), or from the site's entire building stock (for <B10>).

Modules A4-5 (construction phase): A4 is neglected because it is not informed in the reference documents. The mechanical excavation for the foundation of buildings is considered in A5.

Modules B1-7 (use phase): According to SIA 2032 [7], B1 is not taken into consideration (See Figure 4). B2 and B3 are neglected in this iteration. B4 and B5 are assessed through the reference study period (i.e. 60 years) [6]. All the necessary materials, building elements or infrastructures having a service time below this temporal horizon is sought to be replaced and therefore is accounted in the LCA. The service time of the concerned macro-component are described in SIA2032 [7] and the final report of the DUREE project [20]. In our study, B6 belong to the layer "Energy". According to SIA 2032 [7], B7 is not assessed.

Module C1-C4 (end-of-life phase): C1 - C4 have been evaluated and are available in the form of an aggregated sum in the KBOB database [8]. The end-of-life stage includes assumptions about the recycling rate, and the way products are disposed of in Switzerland in recent years [8]. These modules will be further analyzed in greater detail in a future work [21].

Module D: Although module D – Benefits and loads beyond the system boundary – is mentioned in the EN standard, it is omitted in SIA2032 [7]. This module is not considered in our assessment but will be further analyzed in a future work [21].

2.4.2.2 The layer "Energies"

This layer describes the supply of heat and electricity to the neighborhood. It is composed of the necessary infrastructure deployed for the energy system (embodied impacts, evaluated through a bill of material (See Supplementary material 1) and the KBOB database [8]), as well as, the different energy sources necessary to power the system under consideration (e.g. natural gas). The different elements taken in account are presented in Figure 3, as well as those neglected. Elements that could not be accurately assessed on the basis of the received foreground information were modelled using optimistic and pessimistic ranges. For more details, see Appendix 2.

The concept and the design of the energy system is the results of the objectives fixed by the land-use planning regulations [22] and environmental impact statement [23], as well as the design study report for of the heat system deployed in Eglantine [14]. The assessment of the embedded impact of this layer follows the same structure as the one presented in Figure 4. The number of items that are necessary through the service time of the neighborhood are set up in accordance with the Swiss standard SIA 2032 [7] and the research findings of the project [20] (See Table 4).

Item description	Lifetime [y]	Item description	Lifetime [y]
Heat pump	20	PV system	30
Heat exchanger	20	inverter	10
Heat storage	20	Building service inst.	30
Concrete pedestal	60	Gas burner	20
Pipe & insulation	30	Ground-source heat probe	30

Table 4: Summary of the different service lives of the main components of the Energy layer.

Concerning the operational impacts, the quantities used in this study for annual energy consumption are those indicated in the site2000W label renewal document [3] after one year of operation. The same document [3] does not indicate possible electricity exports to the grid. Conflicting data on the type of gas used forced the analysis of two variants, one with biogas and the second with natural gas. The environmental impacts of use stage related to the use of the operational energy, are evaluated using the current characteristics of the energy carriers, i.e. electricity from network (mix consumer and labelled "naturemade") and gas (both biogas and natural gas alternatives have been assessed) [8]. They are assessed on an annual basis and, for simplification purposes, the potential impacts of electricity and gases are considered not to evolve substantially over the entire service life of the neighborhood.

2.4.2.3 The layer "Open Spaces"

The layer "open spaces" contains physical elements that are not buildings nor roads for vehicles. This layer mainly concerns street furniture, outdoor landscaping and pedestrian paths. The inventory is based on GIS surveys and the photographic campaign (see Supplementary material 2). Environmental impacts of these elements were estimated using bills of materials (see Supplementary material 1) in combination with the KBOB database [8] following the structure showed in Figure 4. The elements considered are presented in Figure 3, as well as those neglected. Elements that could not be accurately assessed on the basis of the information received were modelled using optimistic and pessimistic ranges. For more details, see Appendix 2.

2.4.2.4 The layer "Mobility"

The mobility is assessed with the method developed in the Swiss standard SIA 2039 [24] and is based mainly on mobility statistics (top-down) [31]. The model adapts the national transportation average values as a function of correlation factors for various urban parameters (See Table 5) to contextualize the case study to a regional setting (i.e. Morges). The correlation factors worked out in SIA 2039 [24] are based on the Microcensus 2010 [25] devoted to the Swiss national passenger traffic study and are affecting the estimation of daily mobility. The Microcensus 2010 has shown that the occasional mobility (i.e. all journeys involving more than 3 hours outside the usual environment, as well as overnight trips) remains about the same throughout Switzerland.

Description of urban parameters		
Type of municipality	Access to the building by public transport	Availability of a public transport pass
Distance until the next supermarket	Intensity of leisure activities	Availability of a private car
Distance until the next shared car location	Household income	Availability and number of car park location

Table 5: Urban parameters affecting the daily mobility according to the Swiss standard SIA 2039 [24].

The assessment of the environmental impacts generated by the mobility of the people living in the neighborhood, which goes beyond its physical boundaries, includes the environmental effects of the road infrastructure, the involved vehicles, and the required fuel. The non-renewable primary energy factors and greenhouse gas emission coefficients used in relation with the transportation modes are those indicated in the SIA 2039 [24] and evaluated with the mobitool database for the year 2015 [26] – see Appendix 3. The Swiss average annual demand for mobility before correction for local context is taken from the SIA2039 for the year 2015.

Mobility is assessed on an annual basis and, for simplification purposes, its environmental impacts are considered not to change substantially over the entire service life of the neighborhood (i.e. 60 years).

2.4.2.5 The layer "Food"

The Swiss office of statistic (FSO) has established a method to evaluate the greenhouse gas (GHG) footprint of households by category of expenditure [17]. This top-down approach deduces the environmental impacts allocated by the value of products provided by a certain sector. The results of this method – based on statistics for the year 2021 - are used in this study for a preliminary evaluation of the GHG emissions from Eglantine's residents when considering what they eat. Unfortunately, no other environmental impact categories are available in this data source, which limits the scope of the presented results.

Two alternatives are considered to evaluate a potential range of impacts from food consumption of residents in Eglantine. First, we consider the number of residences, which is a fixed number containing no uncertainties in our case study. This number is therefore used in direct relation with the study [17] and generate the upper limit of the assessment for the food layer. According to FSO, the national statistic reveals a mean average of 2.18 person per residence in 2021, leading to 1031 residents for Eglantine. The second alternative corresponds to a lower limit given by the number of inhabitants (777.4) that is informed in the 2000W certification file [3].

2.4.2.6 The layer "Consumption"

The consumption layer of the model is based on the same reference documents as for the food layer [29]. The results of this top-down method, based on statistics for the year 2021, are used in this study for the evaluation of the GHG emissions from the consumption of Eglantine's residents. As for the food layer, no other environmental impact categories are provided in this data source.

The consumption quantities are evaluated on the basis of the Swiss average income and assumed to be representative for the average of residents living the neighborhood. The evaluation of the lower and higher numbers of residents is the same as the one presented in section 2.4.2.5.

2.5 LCA Results and discussion

An overview of the LCA results disaggregated for the six considered layers of the system is shown in Table 6 with ranges that consider best- and worst-case situations. The ranges are obtained from the various models used to capture contributors (see Appendix 2) as defined in the descriptions of Section 2.4.2. Following the defined functional unit (see Section 2.4), the results are presented per year for all impact categories that can be assessed using the data sources selected for this study.

Layers	UBP		CED		CEDr		CEDnr		GHG	
	Embodied impacts [UBP/y]	Operational impacts [UBP/y]	Embodied impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Operational impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Embodied impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Operational impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Embodied impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Operational impacts [kWh _{oil-eq} /y]	Embodied impacts [kg CO _{2-eq} /y]	Operational impacts [kg CO _{2-eq} /y]
min	1050208505		3186432		1349267		1936937		635719	
 moy	1319496821	no OI	3607253	no OI	1361968	no OI	2345066	no OI	802989	
max	1599207421		4062754		1376871		2785620		981043	
min	260906712	156841817	474673	1732620	35257	1663865	388192	68754	95931	41862
<E> moy	268871624	163785972	492492	1775101	35519	1665381	405797	109720	100069	48047
max	276836536	170730128	513905	1762321	37649	1666898	425965	95423	104894	54233
min	40374301		87481		11232		76149		22310	
<OS> moy	47990064	no OI	103161	no OI	12015	no OI	91024	no OI	26508	
max	55605827		118842		12798		105899		30707	
min			3527504		157039		3370464		687370	
<M> moy	not available with SIA2039		4103184		182668		3920517		799547	
max			4678865		208296		4470569		911725	
min									2083404	
<C> moy	not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		2458059	
max									2832714	
min									1317258	
<F> moy	not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		not available with this evaluation method		1554138	
max									1791018	

Table 6: Environmental impact results for the Eglantines neighborhood

The impact category relating to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is the most documented across the analyzed layers. As this is the only impact category that allows comparison between all contributors, a visualization of these results is proposed in Figure 5 where the results are presented per year and in relation to the total amount of SRE surface in all buildings of the neighborhood.

Figure 5: Annual GHG emission (absolute values showed in the left, and relative values in the table on the right) at the neighborhood scale according to the examined dimension.

The relative importance of the layers varies from one impact category to another. To illustrate this, we show all the results obtained for the layers that are informed by the KBOB database [8] in Figure 6. The absolute values at the top of each column indicates values per year related to the full neighborhood.

Figure 6: Relative importance of the "Buildings" layer, embedded Impacts of the "Energies" layer, operative impacts of the "Energies" layer, and "Open spaces" layer (respectively , <E_E>, <E_O>, <OS> in the figure) for the different impact categories available in the KBOB database [8].

A detailed discussion of the results for each layer is presented in the following sub-section, following the relative weight of the layers' greenhouse gas emission contributions.

2.5.1 The layer "Consumption"

Figure 7 presents the different dimensions of consumption comprised in the layer "Consumption" and their shares in term of GHG emissions. The values correspond to the national average and have been assessed by the Swiss Federal Office of Statistics with a monetary input-output analysis [17]. As mentioned before, this source of information only offers information on the GHG emissions in CO₂-eq values. The share of GHG emissions due to importation of these same dimensions are disclosed in Figure 8. The remainder is attributable to indirect domestic GHG emissions with the exception of the category "other goods & services" in which 2.4% of the total can be allocated to direct emissions of the households.

It is expected that the results obtained for the layer Consumption with a top-down approach will be more significant than those that would be obtained with a bottom-up inventory approach. It must be understood that services and the transport of goods from the purchase point to the neighborhood are not taken into account in a bottom-up LCA approach [27].

Figure 7: Share of the GHG emission of the Consumption layer.

Figure 8: Share of emission due to importation of the "Consumption" layer.

2.5.2 The layer "Food"

Evaluated through data provided by the FSO in the same way as the layer "Consumption", the layer "Food" comprises food products, alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages and tobacco, but does not include food served in establishments (restaurants, hotels, hospitals, etc.). The values assessed in this study correspond to Swiss national average. GHG emissions from imports account for 63.2% of the total, the rest being associated with the emission of inner economy; no direct GHG emissions from households is reported in the FSO study [17].

It is possible to compare our results with the "standard" results for European residents. Tucker et al [28], have estimated that the environmental impact of food represents around 20-30% of an individual's consumption. In the present study, the share of the layer "Food" represents 28% of the sum of the different layers.

The great volatility of food consumption behavior is well known. For example a budget survey [29] made in Switzerland (n=3238 individuals) exhibit GHG emissions varying from 80 [kg CO₂ -eq. y⁻¹*p⁻¹] to 5 [t CO₂ -eq. y⁻¹*p⁻¹], with a median value of 1 and a mean of 1.1 [t CO₂ -eq. y⁻¹*p⁻¹] for on-home food with alcoholic beverage but without tobacco. It is therefore often difficult for the public to identify themselves

with an average value. In comparison to the value presented in Table 6 and Figure 5 corresponding in our assessment to 2 [t CO₂-eq. y⁻¹*p⁻¹], Jungbluth et al. [27] quantified the national emissions of food, beverage, and tobacco product consumption to slightly over 10 Mt CO₂ eq. per year (which corresponds to 1.3 t CO₂ eq. per capita) in a Swiss environmentally extended input–output analysis for the year 2005. As for the layer Consumption and due to the same nature of the model, it is expected to have more significant results compared with a bottom-up inventory approach [27].

2.5.3 The layer "Buildings"

The environmental impacts presented here are embedded impacts only. When we take a closer look at greenhouse gas emissions (see Figure 9), we see that preparatory work and structures (e.g. slabs) are the biggest contributors.

Proportion of the GHG emissions, Layer

Figure 9: Breakdown of "Buildings" layer contributors for the greenhouse gas emissions impact category.

Comparison of the results obtained with similar cases of contemporary construction reported in the literature informs us on the relevance of the order of magnitude of our values. The study by Kröhnert et al. (2022) [30], specifically for a conventionally constructed building, reveals emissions of 10,7 [kg CO₂-eq*m⁻²_{SRE}*y⁻¹] for the construction, maintenance and end-of-life stages (see Figure 10). This is smaller than the range of our results between 13 and 20 [kg CO₂-eq*m⁻²_{SRE}*y⁻¹] (See Figure 5). The difference is explained by the fact that the building studied in [30] has only one basement and no underground parking lot.

Figure 10: Extract from Kröhnert et al. (2022) [30].

Figure 11 : Extract from Häfliger et al. (2017) [31].

Another comparison, this time with the Häfliger et al. study (2017) [31] is depicted in Figure 10 (bar MFH02), where a multi-family building of medium inertia construction (building made with a mix of wood and concrete as structural materials) demonstrates emissions of 16 [kg CO₂-eq·m⁻²_{SRE}·y⁻¹] when using KBOB as a background data source. This value fits within the range of our results going from 13 to 20 [kg CO₂-eq·m⁻²_{SRE}·y⁻¹] (see Figure 5). The comparison of results with different background databases suggests the importance of using a consistent source of information to make comparison between this study and others.

2.5.4 The layer "Mobility"

The third contributor, mobility, is a dimension of neighborhood activities where the potential for GHG reduction through technical, collective or behavioral changes could be substantial. While GHG emissions amount is evaluated to be about the same amount as the “buildings” layer, mobility is much more energy-intensive, especially in its non-renewable part. Assessments presented in Table 6 are made with the model assuming the mobility framework presented in SIA2039 [24]. The modal repartition is estimated by applying the correction factors specific to the case studied (see Figure 12). Since the correction factors proposed in [24] are not the same for the primary energy and the CO₂-eq emissions, two values are therefore obtained and shown in Table 6.

Figure 12: Modal split for the Eglantine neighborhood, estimated using the SIA 2039 tool [24]. On the left, daily mobility for Eglantine is shown in relation to the Swiss national average. Occasional mobility is shown on the right.

Known to all public policies, the availability of parking spaces and garages on the neighborhood site is a parameter that correlates with individual mobility behavior patterns (section 2.2.2.1 of SIA 2039 [24]. From Figure 12 and compared with the Swiss average, we expect an increase on the distance travelled by cars in Eglantine to the detriment of public transport and active mobility.

2.5.5 The layer "Energies"

The nature of the fuel used for heating purpose is currently uncertain (See section 2.5.2) and this can substantially affect the results of our assessment. Conflicting data on the type of gas used forced the analysis of two variants, one with biogas and the second with natural gas. Figure 13 disclose the difference obtained whether the system is powered by biogas or natural gas.

Figure 13: CED, CEDnr, UBP and GHG emissions, divided into operational impacts and embedded impacts of the burner and the fuel used, depending on if biogas or natural gas is chosen in the assessment.

The breakdown of greenhouse gas emissions for the full "Energies" layer is 67.6% for the embedded impacts and the remainder for the operational phase. The consequence of an elaborate energy system allows for a smaller impact at the operational level ($1 \text{ [kg CO}_2\text{-eq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\text{SRE}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}]$) (see Figure 5), but the sum of the layer "Energies" ($3 \text{ [kg CO}_2\text{-eq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\text{SRE}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}]$) fits well with the number of Kröhnert et al. (2022) [30] in Figure 10.

The current assessment does not include possible electricity exports. Figure 5 indicates the GHG emissions of the operational part of the "Energies" layer to be only to 1% of the total.

2.5.6 The layer "Open Spaces"

Exterior fittings are not included in Swiss environmental impact assessment standards such as SIA 2040 [6] or SIA2032 [7]. Although those concerning Eglantines are generally much more substantial than the average open space equipment for houses, their impact seems derisory compared to other contributors of the neighborhood (See Figure 5).

2.5.7 Towards a more environmentally sustainable Eglantine neighborhood

The results provide some ideas on general recommendations for improving the environmental footprint of the analyzed neighborhood. They are presented here in order of importance to support the reduction of direct and indirect environmental impacts.

Concerning layer <F>: Buy and eat locally. Sharing the idea of the environmental benefits of vegetarian diets and reduced food waste [32]. Of the 330 [kg/y*p] of food currently wasted in Switzerland, 28% is wasted at home [33].

Concerning layer <C>: Extend the lifespan of everyday consumer goods [34] and favor local products when possible.

Concerning : Density use and extend the lifespan of building infrastructures with neighborhood activities that support maintenance of the shared spaces.

For <M>: Revisit modes of mobility, for residents, workers and customers alike, by promoting public transport for example. Adopting electric cars could enable an environmental footprint reduction without changing the habits of the residents. Increased use of public transport should also be considered, given the neighborhood 's excellent centrality in a fast-growing region.

Regarding the layer <E>, a change in the energy consumption of residents will bring limited gains in terms of environmental impacts, but use of biogas would be beneficial.

The low intensity of the results obtained for the <OS> are linked to the fact that no major infrastructure works were hypothesized during the 60 years analyzed in the study. Not many recommendations can be given beyond the extension of lifetime for the exterior equipment.

2.6 Discussion on the used method

The model comprises six layers, evaluated iteratively almost independently. Silo work in each of these layers can be reductive, especially for cross-cutting aspects such as the use of energy. The classification of elements within a given layer is therefore entirely arbitrary. A good example of this is the (debatable) decision to list the operational energy of means of locomotion in the "Mobility" layer rather than the "Energies" layer.

A better LCA model would consist in the use of same methodology for all the layers. For obvious reasons of project resources, it is difficult to imagine carrying out a bottom-up study of consumption and eating habits in the Eglantine district. In this study, the developed model is hybrid in the sense that it combines LCA data based on a bottom-up LCA approach, with an environmental extended input-output approach for layers <C> and <F>. The results obtained for these two layers are therefore expected to be bigger than those that could be obtained using a bottom -up inventory method. Mobility is deduced using a

normative tool based mainly on mobility statistics, which should still be highly comparable to the bottom-up approach since environmental data is linked to LCA databases.

The choice and use of the environmental databases determine the quantity of environmental impact indicators available. The use of KBOB data source thus limit the analysis to a few impact categories concerning the quantity of greenhouse gases, the quantity of renewable and non-renewable primary energy and the UBP ecological saturation scores. Unfortunately, KBOB does not specifically include indicators of land use or freshwater ecotoxicity. As suggested in the study of Krönert et al. [30], it would be interesting to consider an indicator on particle matter to inform us about diseases caused by emissions of particles with diameter smaller than 2.5 μm . In the construction sector, these emissions come in a prominent manner from the excavation, from the dismantling phases of concrete structures and carpets. Also, the KBOB database [8] is often lacking in description of its activities, and some important construction elements are simply not listed (e.g. water infrastructure, soil and landscaping).

Although the neighborhood is of recent construction, gathering and curating information has not been easy, leaving little hope of having small ranges of uncertainty. The challenge will be all the greater for neighborhoods that have been shaped by history. Also, possible site visits only provide information on the visible aspects. Furthermore, on-site photography can be problematic if unannounced, as demonstrated by the police's interruption of the April 2025 photo campaign (see Supplementary material 2).

At the moment, the possibility of automating the LCA evaluation is limited for Eglantine. It was carried out by hand using a spreadsheet program (see supplementary material 1). The vectorized building layer provided by the Swiss Confederation [35] only provides information on elements above the surface and does not yet contain the newly built neighborhood of Eglantine. Also, the RegBL (see Supplementary material 3) offers no information on the underground levels of buildings that play a decisive role in the environmental assessment of the construction sector. The current development in terms of digital twins could help to rapidly establish an inventory of materials used in the areas under investigation.

Regarding the assessment of the mobility, using up-to-date Microcensus (post-COVID: not yet available) and up-to-date Mobitool factor taking in account the real penetration rate of electric vehicle could be a great improvement on the representativeness of the model. To uncover the reasons and choices of locomotion behind the distances covered by each mean of transport would possibly allow the identification of potential synergies at the community level leading to possible environmental gains.

Regarding the energy, the possible exports of PV electricity should be addressed since they can influence greatly the environmental balance for the neighborhood. Electric vehicle recharging stations should also be further assessed, for both operational and embedded impacts.

This first LCA iteration together with the chosen functional unit enable the identification of environmental hotspots in the neighborhood of investigation, i.e. Eglantine. A proposal to sharpen the definition of functional unit has been proposed by the authors in [36]. Ultimately a proper functional unit should allow to follow the evolution and transformation of a neighborhood over time and/or the comparison with other neighborhoods that provide similar services to its residents.

3 Conclusion

The analysis of the development of an LCA study applied to the Eglantine neighborhood and the results obtained from the first iteration are the subject of the task T3.2.2 "Global diagnosis of the neighborhoods" of the SWICE project.

The proposed approach has an iterative aspect that is specific to LCA. Initially, an LCA diagnosis is used to identify the hotspots in terms of environmental burdens. That is the subject of this report. The intermediate steps are to inform the stakeholders of the nature of the results in order to co-create efficient transformation scenarios that could lead to environmental gains. The final step would consist in the selection of beneficial and acceptable scenarios to be implemented. These new scenarios could then be evaluated with the LCA method and the environmental benefits for the neighborhood could then be checked.

The model developed here is considered to be hybrid, since it combines three layers evaluated using a "bottom-up" KBOB database, two layers evaluated on a "top-down" economic basis and one "top-down" model of mobility based on national statistics.

Although this is a rather recent neighborhood, the difficulty of gathering information to carry out an inventory of the neighborhood's components is nonetheless persistent. This difficulty is reflected in the significant uncertainties surrounding the obtained LCA results.

The main objective of this first iteration has been achieved: the hotspots associated with the neighborhood's environmental impact contributions have been highlighted. These hotspots are in particular the household consumption and the nutrition. In term of infrastructure, it has been shown that the underground parking is responsible of around one fifth of the embedded impact of the layer Buildings, and at the same time may amplify the use of personal cars. Provided that the buildings deployed last as long as planned, the potential for changing the environmental footprint is in the hands of the inhabitants, through their choices of consumption habits and mobility.

Based on the results obtained from the environmental diagnosis of Eglantine, general recommendations are formulated for a reduction of the environmental footprint of the neighborhood. Their impacts should be estimated at a later stage of the project.

Further development of the present LCA method and its applicability to other case studies will depend, in particular, on the development of the functional unit concept to make it applicable to a wide range of neighborhoods.

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Nomenclature

Symbol	Description	Unit
	Layer "Building"	
<OS>	Layer "Open spaces"	
<E>	Layer "Energy"	
<M>	Layer "Mobility"	
<F>	Layer "Food"	
<C>	Layer "Consumption"	
GHG	Greenhouse gas emission	[kg CO ₂ -eq]
CED	Cumulative energy demand	[kWh oil-eq]
CED,nr	Non renewable part of CED	[kWh oil-eq]
CEDr	Renewable part of CED	[kWh oil-eq]
UBP	Umweltbelastungspunkte	[-]
[OI]	Operational impact	
[EI]	Embedded Impact	
FTE	Full time equivalent	
SRE	Energy reference area	m ² SRE

Appendices

Appendix 1: Comparison of assessment with different international framework, adapted from [43]

Figure 3: Comparison of building element groups by life cycle assessment, by country.

Appendix 2: Optimistic and pessimistic models of components

Layer	Description	Optimistic	mean	Pessimistic
<OS>	Urban furniture precast concrete 0,6*0,6	450 [m _{lin}]	472	500
<OS>	excavation ground, volume	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	concrete	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	Asphalte	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	gravel base deep-bottom	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	Paving bed	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	gravel	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
<OS>	Paving	measured x 0,8	measured	measured x 1,2
	excavation ground, volume	measured x 1.0	measured	measured x1,5
	<Water depletion>	no		yes
	Drilling piles	no		yes
	Finishing excavation	studded walls		underpinned Parisian walls
	Kitchen plan	small, standard quality		Long, best quality
	Kitchen, work plan	synthetic		chrome-plated, high-end
	Element for kitchen	wood		metal
	Cupboard & sink	composite		chrome - steel
	internal wall	0.75*SIA2047	values SIA 2047	1.5*SIA2047
<E>	Excavation shielding	no		yes
<E>	depth distric heating	1.3		2
<E>	diameter pipes PE for electricity	8 x PE DN50		16 x PE DN50
<E>	Ventilation mass-flow in shops	1 m3/h		8 m3/h
<E>	Ventilation material ducts	low grade		high grade
<E>	sanitary facilities	easy, low-end		complex, high-end
<E>	gas	biogas		Natural gas
<C>	number of concerned people	777.4		2.18 x 473 housings
<F>	number of concerned people	777.4		2.18 x 473 housings

Appendix 3: Mobitool conversion factors from [24]

Tableau 62 Taux d'occupation, consommation de carburant, facteurs d'énergie primaires non renouvelables (FEP_{nren}) et coefficients d'émissions de gaz à effet de serre (CEGES pour différents moyens de transport (année 2014) selon [11] et mobitool [6])

Moyen de transport	Unité	Voiture particulière ⁴¹	Moyenne trafic régional et trafic longue distance	Train longue distance	Train régional	Bus urbain	Tram	Moto, vélomoteur	Vélo	Avion
Taux moyen d'occupation		1,6	167	392	46	14	53	1,1	1	279
Besoin spécifique de carburant par kilomètre-véhicule	kg kWh	0,07	17 ⁴²	33	8	0,35	4,8	0,03	-	8,7
FEP _{nren} kWh par kilomètre-véhicule, dont	kWh	1,44	23,5	45,0	10,4	6,4	15,9	0,471	0,039	166,9
– Exploitation		1,06	17,2	31,1	8,0	5,3	11,8	0,400	0,0	141,7
– Énergie grise dans véhicule et infrastructure routière		0,38	6,3	13,9	2,3	1,1	4,1	0,070	0,039	25,2
FEP _{nren} kWh par kilomètre-personne, dont	kWh	0,897	0,141	0,115	0,224	0,456	0,300	0,428	0,039	0,597
– Exploitation		0,658	0,103	0,079	0,174	0,378	0,224	0,364	0,000	0,508
– Énergie grise dans véhicule et infrastructure routière		0,239	0,038	0,035	0,051	0,076	0,078	0,064	0,039	0,090
CEGES kg par kilomètre-véhicule, dont	kg	0,32	1,32	2,66	0,48	1,46	1,37	0,135	0,009	39,97
– Exploitation		0,27	0,21	0,29	0,07	1,33	0,60	0,121	0,000	35,00
– Énergie grise dans véhicule et infrastructure routière		0,05	1,10	2,37	0,40	0,13	0,77	0,014	0,009	4,97
CEGES kg par kilomètre-personne, dont	kg	0,197	0,008	0,007	0,010	0,104	0,026	0,123	0,009	0,143
– Exploitation		0,166	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,095	0,011	0,110	0,000	0,125
– Énergie grise dans véhicule et infrastructure routière		0,031	0,007	0,006	0,009	0,009	0,015	0,013	0,009	0,018

Supplementary materials

(Available in electronic format upon request to the member of the SWICE research consortium)

Supplementary material 1: Excel files containing inventory and impact assessments.

Supplementary material 2: On-site photo campaign.

Supplementary material 3: Excerpt from RegBL datasheet of the buildings inside the perimeter of study.

Supplementary material 4: database KBOB 2009_1_2022_V5 (issued 15/07/2024).